

This project has received funding from
The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
Grant agreement No 101017562

**Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning
FEMaLe**

Call/Topic: Digital transformation in Health and Care
Type of action: RIA

Date: 12.02.2025

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	9.10
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Exploitation of results plan, M47
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Semmelweis University (P5)
GRANT AGREEMENT No.	101000640
DOCUMENT TYPE	Report
WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	9 – BEACON
LEAD CONTRACTOR	Semmelweis University
AUTHOR(S)	Dóra Bianka Balogh, Boglárka Barkó, and all Beneficiaries
PLANNED DELIVERY DATE	November 30 th , 2024
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	February 12 th , 2025
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
STATUS	Reviewed and quality checked
VERSION	Final version (1.5)
REVIEWED BY	FEMaLE PMO

Document history

Version	Date ¹	Comment	Author	Status ²
1.1	25-11-2024	First draft created	SEMM	Drafted
1.2	17-12-2024	Second draft created, including recommendations from WP participants.	SEMM	Drafted
1.3	07-01-2025	Third draft prepared for FEMaLe Review Panel.	SEMM	Drafted
1.4	31-01-2025	Final draft created, based on FEMaLe Review Panel feedback.	SEMM	Completed
1.5	05-02-2025	Final version ready for submission, quality checked by FEMaLe PMO.	AU	Validated

¹ As per the project's cloud storage or per email date if applicable.

² Drafted, completed or validated as per the project's cloud storage or per email date if applicable.

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Acknowledgement

The project 'Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning' (FEMaLe) has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 programme under grant number 101000640.

Citation

Be so kind as to cite this work as: Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning, 2025: Exploitation of results plan, M47 – under the supervision of the Project's Coordinator.

Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of I Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

WP9. BEACON: dissemination, communication, and synergies

D9.10 – Exploitation of results plan, M47

1. Exploitation of results plan

The purpose of this plan is to ensure that the results from the FEMaLe project do not *only* lead to academic publications but also create value for healthcare systems, patients, and society at large. The primary focus is on implementation, innovation, and raising awareness of endometriosis, including:

Engaging (Citizen) Science Communication

- Publishing research results in open-access journals to ensure availability (see page 6).
- Producing content that conveys research findings in non-academic language (see page 7).
- Presentations at conferences, symposia, and relevant network meetings (see page 8).
- Participation in (inter)national multiplier events to promote FEMaLe (see page 9).

Awareness Raising and Information Sharing across Europe

Co-Creation, Campaigns, and Political Awareness

- Co-created social media campaigns to raise endometriosis awareness in Europe (see page 10).
- Engaging patients to ensure findings are benefitting those directly affected (see page 11).
- Engaging in dialogue with Policymakers and Members of Parliaments about the urgent and unmet need for a cohesive cross-country approach to combat endometriosis (see page 12).

Innovation Development

- FEMaLe outputs and corresponding TRLs over time (see page 13).
- Development of Go-to-Market strategies (see pages 14-22).

FEMaLe Legacy

- *EUmetriosis* (see page 22).
- *READI* (see page 23).

a. Partners and Stakeholders

FEMaLe project engages academic researchers, industry partners, policymakers, and regulators to maximize impact. Stakeholder involvement ensures research aligns with diverse needs, enhances transparency, and fosters trust. Their insights shape the project's direction, execution, and dissemination, reinforcing social and ethical responsibility.

Table 1.1 shows the list of the 15 FEMaLe advisers recruited since the beginning of the project.

No.	Name	Representing	Label
#1	Annalise Weckesser	Social Sciences Endometriosis Network, Birmingham University, UK	Research
#2	Dorthe Hartwell	Dept. of Gynaecology, Copenhagen University Hospital, Denmark	Clinician
#3	Engin Oral	Endometriosis and Adenomyosis Society, Turkey	Clinician
#4	Francesco Mureddu	The Lisbon Council, Belgium	Policy
#5	Harald Krentel	European Endometriosis League, Germany	Clinician
#6	Maria Tomlinson	Dept. of Journalism Studies, The University of Sheffield, UK	Research
#7	Marina Kvaskoff	National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), France	Research
#8	Martin Götte	Dept. of Gynecology and Obstetrics, University of Münster, Germany	Research
#9	Stacey Missmer	Michigan State University, the US	Research
#10	Annemiek Nap	Radboud University and Radboudumc, The Netherlands	Clinician
#11	Femke Jansen	World Endometriosis Organizations (WEO), UK	Research
#12	Horace Roman	Endometriosis Center, Clinique Tivoli-Ducos, Bordeaux, France	Clinician
#13	Bianca Schor	PhD student, Alan Turing Institute, Cambridge Computer Lab, UK	Research
#14	Bharati Shivalkar	Delta (CHIREC) Hospital, Belgium	Clinician
#15	Annemette Broch	DATA for GOOD Foundation, Denmark	IT/Tech

Table 1.1

2. Scientific outputs

FEMaLers actively contribute to scientific research, publishing in top-tier journals, conferences, and workshops. Their goal is to share findings, foster collaborations, and enhance the project's visibility, impact, and recognition within the scientific community.

a. Full-paper publications

Table 2.1 shows the eight scientific articles that have been published in the final year of the project.

#	Title	Journal	Published	DOI
1	Endometriosis: time to think differently (and together)	<i>British Journal of General Practice</i>	01 May, 2024	https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp24X737085
2	FEMaLe: The use of machine learning for early diagnosis of endometriosis based on patient self-reported data — Study protocol of a multicenter trial	<i>PLOS One</i>	09 May, 2024	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0300186
3	Digital Health for Improved Endometriosis Research and Care	<i>Birinci Basamak Sağlık Hizmetlerinde E-Sağlık Uygulamaları ve Geleceği</i>	05 Oct, 2024	https://www.turkiyeklinikeri.com/article/tr-digital-health-for-improved-endometriosis-research-and-care-109022.html
4	Exploring pre-diagnosis hospital contacts in women with endometriosis using ICD-10: Danish case-control study	<i>Human Reproduction</i>	20 Dec, 2024	https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deae273
5	Understanding endometriosis underfunding and its detrimental impact on awareness and research	<i>npj Women's Health</i>	21 Dec, 2024	https://doi.org/10.1038/s44294-024-00048-6
6	Association between endometriosis and working life among Danish women	<i>Human Reproduction</i>	11 Jan, 2025	https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deae298
7	Consensus on Symptom Selection for Endometriosis Questionnaires: A Modified e-Delphi Study	<i>BJOG</i>	13 Jan, 2025	https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.18066
8	Prevalence and sociodemographic distribution of endometriosis symptoms and indicators in Denmark	<i>European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology</i>	31 Jan, 2025	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2025.01.051

Table 2.1

b. Popularised publications

Table 2.2 shows selected popularised publication that have been published in the final FEMaLe year.

No.	Title	Journal	Publication date	Link
1	Skal det virkelig være så svært? Kvindelige patienters sygdomme overses	Kristeligt Dagblad	20 March, 2024	https://www.kristeligt-dagblad.dk/debat/skal-det-virkelig-vaere-saa-svaert-kvindelige-patienters-sygdomme-overses
2	Forskere om invaliderende kvindesygdom: Ny forskning sker i udlandet, ikke her, selvom vi nok ville kunne gøre det bedre	<i>Berlingske</i>	27 June, 2024	https://www.berlingske.dk/kronikker/frustrerede-forskere-om-endometriose-ny-forskning-sker-i-udlandet-ikke
3	Debat: Endometriose er ikke bare en kvindesygdom	<i>Jyllands-Posten</i>	01 July, 2024	https://jyllands-posten.dk/debat/breve/ECE17228326/endometriose-er-ikke-bare-en-kvindesygdom/
4	Debat: Opgør med tabuer om kvinders smerter og sygdomme	Kristeligt Dagblad	12 August, 2024	https://www.kristeligt-dagblad.dk/debat/politikere-klar-tid-til-opgoer-med-tabuer-om-kvinders-smerter-og-sygdomme
5	Overlæge slår alarm: »Den næste patient, der bliver henvist til os, kan vi først se omkring 1. juni 2025«	<i>Politiken</i>	13 October, 2024	https://politiken.dk/danmark/sundhed/art10097803/Overl%C3%A6ge-sl%C3%A5r-alarm-%C2%BBDen-n%C3%A6ste-patient-der-bliver-henvist-til-os-kan-vi-f%C3%B8rst-se-omkring-1.-juni-2025%C2%AB
6	Smerterne er uudholdelige: »Jeg har besteget bjerge på størrelse med Mount Everest siden 2016«	<i>Politiken</i>	14 October, 2024	https://politiken.dk/danmark/sundhed/art10097797/Smerterne-er-uudholdelige-%C2%BBJeg-har-besteget-bjerge-p%C3%A5-st%C3%B8rrelse-med-Mount-Everest-siden-2016%C2%AB
7	Ondt i underlivet	<i>Politiken</i>	16 October, 2024	https://politiken.dk/debat/art10117713/Sygdomme-der-kun-rammer-kvindeskroppe-skal-tages- alvorligt
8	Dansk Erhverv: Manglende fokus på kvinders sundhed koster milliarder	<i>Politiken</i>	12 December, 2024	https://politiken.dk/danmark/sundhed/art10180076/Forskels%C2%ADbehandling-af-syge-kvinder-er-enorm.-Nu-lanceres-tre-nye-ideer
9	Kronik: Center for kvinders sundhed skal gøre op med uligheden i sundhed	<i>Jyllands-Posten</i>	26 December, 2024	https://jyllands-posten.dk/debat/kronik/ECE17742879/center-for-kvinders-sundhed-skal-goere-op-med-uligheden-i-sundhed/

Table 2.2

c. Abstracts and attendance

The partners are continuously informed about relevant scientific events, and they are advised to submit abstracts and present results. The partners are encouraged to participate in such events to present FEMaLe work, highlight its impacts and gain knowledge about the to-date research and innovation in the field. The following talks have been given in the final year of the FEMaLe project:

January 2024: Nilufer Rahmioglu gave an invited talk at the *Festival of Genomics* and at the *Annual Academic Meeting of Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists* in London.

February 2024: Nilufer Rahmioglu and Krina Zondervan gave invited talks at the *Endometriosis and Adenomyosis: Bench to Bedside* conference in Istanbul, Türkiye. Mette Nyegaard participated as an invited expert in a closed hearing by the Health Committee of the Danish Parliament.

April 2024: Krina Zondervan gave an invited talk at the conference organised by the *Society of Endometriosis and Uterine Disorders (SEUD)*.

May 2024: Nilufer Rahmioglu presented for Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences at the University of Surrey in the UK.

June 2024: Eeva-Liisa Johansen and Marie Josiasen presented the results from studies related to work-years lost and geographical distribution of endometriosis related symptoms, respectively, at the *Nordic Epidemiological Conference* in Copenhagen (poster presentations). Moreover, Krina Zondervan gave an invited talk at the *7th European Endometriosis Congress* in Bucharest, Romania.

August 2024: Krina Zondervan gave an invited talk at the *IASP 2024 World Congress on Pain*.

September 2024: Ulrik Bak Kirk presented the exciting results of the FEMaLe Project for the Health Committee of the Danish Parliament.

October 2024: Mintu Nath presented the poster 'a population-based study to assess the incidence of endometriosis and its association with demographic characteristics in England' at the European Society for Gynecological Endoscopy (ESGE) 33rd Annual Congress held in Marseille, France. In addition, Luck Saraswat received an award for the best abstract presented at the 33rd ESGE congress.

November 2024: Anna Melgaard and Dorte Rytter presented the FEMaLe Project at an event for the *Aarhus Reproductive Epidemiological Network*. In addition, they presented the project for the *Danish Medical Association in Southern Denmark* with approximately 50 doctors in person and 570 doctors more from the entire country attending online.

December 2024: Two major events in Copenhagen; Dagens Medicin and Final FEMaLe Conference.

d. Multiplier and External Events

FEMaLers have participated in a series of different national and international multiplier events to raise awareness of the project, engage with specialist groups of stakeholders, and disseminate the project results. In recognition of *Endometriosis World Day 2024*, Hungarian partner TOGETHER organized an impressive *EndoMarch* roadshow across Hungary, raising awareness through a series of impactful events.

Throughout 2024, IAAD, with the support of Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University (MSKÜ), organized a series of five roundtable discussions, culminating in a conference on 19 December 2024 at MSKÜ in Muğla, Türkiye. These events convened key stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers to collaboratively explore and refine strategies for improving the early diagnosis and treatment of endometriosis. Insights gathered from these discussions were synthesized into actionable recommendations, paving the way for meaningful advancements in women's health.

FEMaLers have also engaged with relevant external events, such as industry conferences, workshops, and exhibitions, where project members showcased their work, networked with industry experts, and explored potential collaboration opportunities with commercial partners.

Norwegian partner Correlate once again showcased the FEMaLe project at *Web Summit 2024*, the world's largest technology event. This premier gathering provided an unparalleled platform for technology leaders to connect, collaborate, and drive innovation in consumer technology.

Moreover, FEMaLers have participated in more meetings with policymakers to discuss the societal and ethical implications of their research and contribute to the development of relevant policies and guidelines, including the urgent and unmet need for dedicated funding and national action plans on endometriosis across Europe. As mentioned, FEMaLers were granted the opportunity to present its project results and advise on future steps before the Danish Ministry of the Interior and Health's Health Committee in February and September 2024.

Lastly, FEMaLe project has leveraged civil society and non-profits to raise awareness about endometriosis and promote digital healthcare adoption. These organizations connect stakeholders, enhance outreach, and drive engagement with early adopters. Endometriosis organizations, collaborating across borders, work with physicians, scientists, and policymakers to improve care and advance research. This approach aligns with the European Commission's goals of fostering citizen engagement and societal impact in research.

3. Raising Awareness and Information Sharing across Europe

FEMaLe Project has contributed to raising awareness and information sharing across Europe in various ways over the past four years. Here are a selected fem examples from the final 12 months:

Engagement and Value of Co-Creation in Social Media Campaigns for the Patient Associations

We launched our second Co-Created Social Media Campaign, this time in close collaboration with the Swedish Endometriosis Patient Association. As part of this campaign, a group of courageous Swedish women and patients with endometriosis volunteered to share photos of their faces, accompanied by self-written quotes that reflected their personal experiences with the condition.

The Swedish #1in10 campaign highlights the crucial role of collective identity in fostering engagement within patient associations. Rooted in a shared experience as 'Endo Warriors', this collective identity cultivated empowerment, solidarity, and a strong sense of community, essential for navigating life with a chronic illness. By aligning participants around common values and goals, it enriched social interactions and strengthened commitment beyond traditional co-creation drivers like shared resources. The campaign's value extended across multiple dimensions, including improved organizational performance, enhanced innovation, increased online brand visibility, and personal and relational benefits for both members and representatives.

Quantitative analysis confirmed its significant reach and online engagement. Despite challenges such as resource limitations and communication gaps, the campaign demonstrated how a strong shared identity can deepen engagement and foster meaningful connections. Participants unanimously expressed a willingness to engage in future co-creation efforts, emphasizing the need for better feedback mechanisms and more consistent two-way communication. The FEMaLe Project played a pivotal role by providing essential resources and strategic guidance, underscoring the importance of external support in driving successful co-creation initiatives within non-profit settings.

This co-creation model could be easily adapted and implemented across Europe, fostering a **broader network of engaged patients** while ensuring that research findings directly benefit those affected by endometriosis. By leveraging digital platforms, shared best practices, and collaborative networks, similar campaigns could **amplify patient voices**, drive advocacy efforts, and enhance knowledge translation. A coordinated European approach would not only strengthen patient-led initiatives but also help researchers and policymakers develop more **patient-centered solutions**, reinforcing the impact of co-created engagement on both a national and international scale.

Enhancing Public Understanding of Women's Health

Associate Professor Felicity Mae Davis and her research team at Aarhus University, alongside FEMaLe's Coordinator Ulrik Bak Kirk, have secured DKK 6 million from the Novo Nordisk Foundation to create an evidence-based museum exhibition in Aarhus ([link to press release](#)).

Inspired by gender disparities in medical research – including the FEMaLe Project's white papers – the science communication project highlights overlooked aspects of female biology, including menstruation, endometriosis, breast development, and reproductive health. Davis hopes the interactive exhibit will spark awareness and inspire change.

Opening on 21 January 2025, *The Overlooked Body* at the Steno Museum explores gender biases in medical research and their impact on diagnosis and treatment. Developed with Aarhus University and Aarhus University Hospital, the exhibition features interactive installations such as a 3D-printed crash test dummy, a contraception imbalance display, and the world's largest knitted placenta by artist Rebecca Vandyk-Hamilton ([link to press release](#)).

The exhibit also sheds light on under-researched conditions like endometriosis and the placenta's medical significance. Visitors can engage with personal stories from women affected by these issues.

A collaboration between researchers, artists, and students, the exhibition will evolve in two phases — an initial display in 2025, followed by an expanded version in 2026 shaped by public input.

The Danish Alliance for Women's Health

In February and September 2024, FEMaLe had the opportunity to present its project results and advise on future steps before the Danish Ministry of the Interior and Health's Health Committee. These presentations were instrumental in the creation of the [Danish Alliance for Women's Health](#), a coalition uniting policymakers and stakeholders to advance women's health.

The alliance focuses on three key objectives:

- Advocating for greater investment in women's health research and innovation.
- Raising awareness of the personal and economic impact of inadequate research.
- Breaking taboos to improve knowledge, data collection, and collaboration in healthcare.

Membership is open to elected politicians at all levels, researchers and professionals in women's health, companies and organizations investing in or promoting women's health, and individuals with expertise or strong interest in the field – individuals can also join as supporting members. Participation is free. The alliance is endorsed by Camilla Fabricius (MP), Monika Rubin (MP), Anne Sophie Callesen, and Marianne Lynghøj.

On 18 February 2025, the Danish Alliance will host its inaugural conference on women's health, and the fully booked event will feature several FEMaLers as speakers and panellists. This Danish way could inspire other countries to establish a similar movement, initiated by elected politicians.

4. Innovation outputs

Innovation is central to the FEMaLe project, driving technological advancements to improve patient quality of life and reduce healthcare costs. Many work packages focus on developing health solutions (as listed in **Table 4.1**) that enhance competitiveness, product quality, and patient protection. The project supports economic growth by fostering new products, services, and market opportunities for EU companies. As innovations mature, their TRLs continue to advance, as outlined in **Table 4.2**.

Table 4.1 shows the list of FEMaLe WPs that are associated with innovation action:

WP	Title	Lead
4	OMICS: risk classifier and biological subtypes	UOXF
5	BIG DATA: digital health monitoring and the Lucy App	SWU
6	DIAGNOSIS: surgical phenotyping using machine learning	RTU
7	VISUAL: augmented reality to improve laparoscopic surgery	SURG
8	DIGITAL: self-management program	YLK

Table 4.1

Table 4.2 shows FEMaLe innovation/technology outputs and their corresponding TRLs over time:

WP	Technology / Innovation	TRL July 2022	TRL NOW	Expected Final TRL
4	2 prototypes of CDS tools (risk stratification tool and multi-marker signature)	2	3	5
5	Lucy app	7	8	9
5	A prototype of the dietary and lifestyle modules	4	5	7
5	A prototype of a global risk profile	1	1	5
6	Software implementing a machine learning based algorithm for the detection and scoring of endometriosis	3	3	5
7	Software implementing a machine learning based algorithm for the suggestion of endometriotic resection zone	2	2	4
8	Implementation of the MY-ENDO program into the modified Lucy app	3	3	5

Table 4.2

5. Business exploitation plan

FEMaLe's innovative solutions (WP4-WP7) will enhance market presence, expand services, and provide a competitive edge for participating companies. By leveraging consortium expertise, FEMaLe aligns on innovation priorities, explores healthcare system integration, and plans commercial strategies, including potential collaborations or joint ventures, to ensure sustainable impact beyond the project.

WP4 | OMICS: risk classification and subtypes

This WP aims to develop two clinical decision tools: 1) a risk stratification tool that uses genes to classify people into high and low risk for endometriosis, and 2) a multi-marker signature to distinguish biological subtypes with the potential to facilitate shared decision-making and guide treatment choice of endometriosis in combination with other information. To achieve this goal, the Scalable Multi-Omics Platform (SMOP) is being developed, driven by FEMaLe partner *PrecisionLife*. This platform transforms multi-omic datasets (genomic, phenotypic, and clinical data) into disease maps. Each disease map reveals a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of complex diseases than traditional GWAS or AI/M methods and enables high-resolution patient stratification.

Innovation/technology: Clinical Decision Support (CDS) tool

FEMaLe partner *PrecisionLife* aims to translate to clinical practice insights generated from the project by developing a **non-invasive, saliva-based CDS tool** for endometriosis (**Figure 5.1**). Ultimately, such a CDS tool will aim to differentially triage endometriosis from other diseases involving deep pelvic pain and identify the mechanisms driving the disease in order to recommend the most effective therapies at an individual patient level.

Figure 5.1. PrecisionLife's CDS tool workflow

Having discovered unique mechanism-based patient stratification for endometriosis and developed the CDS framework as part of the FEMaLe project, *PrecisionLife* aim to seek further clinical validation of our novel CDS tool and prepare for market entry (**Figure 5.2**). Key areas of improvement and innovation will include:

- (1) We will first replicate and refine our endometriosis risk scores following incorporation of large datasets (e.g. All of Us, Our Future Health and Kaiser). This will include validation of further disease protective signatures and use of new diverse ancestry data to further expand health equity and ensure patient representation. We will also select previously identified repurposing candidates and re-analyse their prevalence and effect sizes across diverse ancestries.
- (2) We will update our CDS framework with the finalised signatures, risk score formula, and annotations required for report generation
- (3) We will work with healthcare partners to complete our Go-To-Market plan, develop Target Product Profiles (TPP) to support market targeting and engage payers and regulatory bodies for approval, reimbursement and Health Economic Outcomes Research (HEOR) analysis.
- (4) Clinical trial to demonstrate the predictive accuracy of our mechanostic test. We will work with clinical operational partners, including saliva swab kit manufacturers/distributors, genotyping providers and dry lab environment as well as healthcare partners/clinical sites and Contract Research Organisations (CRO) to execute the trials. We will deploy our CDS tool into a dry lab results reporting environment, as we have in our ongoing Metrodora project. The output of this trial will be publication of predictive accuracy results required to obtain IVDR approval for our mechanostic test.
- (5) Clinical trial to demonstrate efficacy of drug repurposing. We will select the most promising repurposing candidates and dosing levels to treat a targeted group of at-risk endometriosis patients based on the analysis of the previous tasks.

Figure 5.2. *PrecisionLife's Summarised Go-To-Market Plan*

In highly heterogeneous diseases with non-specific symptoms, such as endometriosis, clinicians urgently need a way to triage patients presenting with those symptoms to identify those at highest risk (in order to expediate targeted diagnosis) and to understand the disease drivers (to ensure the most effective, personalised treatment approach). These needs can be expanded for the key stakeholders:

Patients' needs

Rapid, accurate, non-invasive and safe **differential triage** procedure to identify endometriosis disease risk.

Avoidance of unnecessary surgeries when endometriosis is not the cause of deep pelvic pain.

Easy access to affordable and effective **treatments** with low side-effect risks.

Healthcare payer's / providers' needs

Accurately predict an individual's **risk** of developing endometriosis to enable earlier diagnosis, timely intervention and prevent progression or more serious disease, e.g. infertility, ovarian cancer.

Clinically actionable results, identifying the **specific disease subtype** based on **underlying causal mechanisms**, enabling better targeting of precision treatments.

Scalable, affordable, fast (~2 weeks) and easy to administer triaging tests applicable across all endometriosis disease subtypes.

Rapid access to individual patient therapeutic options through repurposed drugs. Aligning with the strong political drive in Europe is pushing to recognize **value-added medicines** as a separate category of medicines with the faster regulation, incentives and reimbursement, akin to the **FDA 505(b)(2)** pathway in the US, which allows previously approved drugs for new indications

The Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe and the **EU General Pharmaceutical Legislation (Article 48)** now allows to submit evidence for **repurposing** authorized medicinal products ([EC Europe, 2023](#)). In cases where the opinion is favourable, marketing authorization holders of the medicinal products concerned shall submit a variation to update the product information with the new therapeutic indication.

Biotech/Pharma needs

Patient stratification biomarkers to enable design of smaller, more targeted clinical trials - selecting only patients who are most likely to respond to treatment, thereby **increasing the chances of clinical success**, and saving significant resources, time and costs.

Demonstration of **proof-of-mechanism of novel drug targets** to modify disease in specific endometriosis patient subgroups based on molecular Mechanisms of Action (MoA), increasing the potential for novel drug programs, therapeutic indication expansions and significant additional revenue generation.

Figure 5.3. How PrecisionLife's work in FEMaLe satisfies market need

The current standard of care for diagnosis remains invasive, expensive and highly variable laparoscopic surgery, usually following often inconclusive pre-operative imaging using MRI or ultrasound. The accuracy of laparoscopy is highly site specific. Overall, surgery fails to visually detect lesions in up to 30% of surgeries and ~50% of biopsies are negative ([Harrison B, 2015](#)). Research efforts are underway to develop non-invasive diagnostic or risk prediction tools, but these are still in various stages of development and validation.

The pipeline for endometriosis diagnostic tools is limited, mainly with early-stage academic projects rather than late-stage commercial trials. Innovation is focused on novel imaging/biopsy techniques (i.e. Oxford University's integrin imaging technology) or novel invasive tests (i.e. Hera Biotech's uterine tissues biopsy solution where a sample of the patient's endometrium is collected using a uterine brush biopsy and analysed using micro-fluidic analysis). The only competing pipeline diagnostics are expensive and as yet unreplicated tests from companies such as Ziwig, Diamens and Dot Laboratories, Inc. which read out disease status based on salivary microRNAs (miRNA) interpreted by 'black box' AI platforms. Ziwig's specificity is low (57%), which is in line with other research studies on miRNA.

Several reasons caused poor results including the potential bias in the control group, as endometriosis could be asymptomatic in up to 20% of patients ([Nisenblat et al., 2016](#)), small sample sizes which cannot rule out all potential biases and the fact there is no evidence to show that single or group of miRNAs can be considered as a sole non-invasive biomarker of endometriosis with key issues including the lack of validated replication, representation of diverse ancestries and representation of confounding diagnoses. Crucially, miRNA and other non-surgical biomarkers (e.g. growth factors, glycoproteins, macrophages, cytokines, TNFs, antibodies, etc.) cannot fully elucidate the specific mechanisms driving the disease.

PrecisionLife has commissioned our IP lawyers Cleveland Scott York to conduct an FTO analysis on the proposed Mechanostic™ product deriving from the FEMaLe project. Based on publicly available databases, the FTO found 99 patents and applications of potential relevance. Of these, 33 were analysed in more detail. No granted patents were found which appear directly relevant to the outputs of this project. Only one granted patent (US10927412) appears somewhat relevant, however, this patent focuses on the determination of the expression level of specified genes of interest (determined by GWAS), rather than more comprehensive combinations of genetic mutations as in our proposed technology. As expected, the majority of the other patents are limited to detection of miRNAs, which is not a feature of our method, and which is less proven and less clinically actionable. No pending applications were found which look likely to grant in a form that would present an obstacle to this project. Furthermore, the use of predicate devices such as TF UK Biobank Axiom™ array means these devices have already been cleared or approved by regulatory bodies, meaning their IP rights have been vetted and are not infringing on existing patents.

All the mutations within our novel signatures are already present on the Axiom UKB microarray, therefore allowing it to be employed for the genotyping. Companies like Thermo Fisher have licensing agreements in place for the technologies used in their arrays, ensuring that users such as *PrecisionLife* are covered under these agreements. In addition, *PrecisionLife* has signed over 35 data access agreements, all granting commercial R&D rights.

Overall, our approach to mechanism-based patient stratification is both highly differentiated and well protected from replication, built on multiple technical innovations, each one of which creates a barrier to entry.

WP5 | BIG DATA: digital health monitoring and the Lucy App

Lucy App offers potential as a digital tool for self-assessment and management of endometriosis symptoms by patients. WP5 leverages a modified version of *Lucy App* to recruit a large cohort, identifying clinical subgroups based on digital footprints, symptoms, and lifestyle patterns.

In FEMaLe Project, *Lucy App* has amassed 20,000 users, logging over 3 million data entries, with 12,000 monthly and 1,500 daily active users. Preliminary analysis of 520,000 self-reported records reveals strong correlations between reported symptoms and known clinical manifestations of endometriosis, demonstrating the reliability of patient-generated health data. With 16,926 users completing at least five daily logs, medical status classifications have been established, enabling robust data-driven insights.

To enhance accuracy, an initial data-filtering process addressed inconsistencies, while XGBoost was applied to identify key symptom patterns and predict endometriosis. Additionally, a longitudinal study, supported by 12,300 first-time questionnaire completions, underscores *Lucy App's* potential for long-term monitoring.

These findings highlight the transformative role of mobile health applications in bridging gaps in traditional medical tracking, advancing early detection, and enabling personalized management. Evolving from a not-for-profit initiative, *Lucy App* is poised to become an innovative platform for medical research, offering unprecedented accessibility to participant data.

Innovation/technology: Modified Lucy App

Over the years, *Lucy App* has successfully evolved into a trusted digital tool for tracking menstrual health, educating users, and prompting timely medical consultations. However, to sustain and expand its reach, *Lucy App* must transition from a non-profit model to a financially self-sustaining platform, ensuring long-term stability and innovation.

To maintain free access to core features while enabling further development, we propose a subscription-based ***Lucy Premium*** model. Premium users will gain access to advanced functionalities, enhancing personalized health insights and user engagement. Transitioning to the freemium model will enable *Lucy App* to achieve financial sustainability, ensuring continuous feature development and international expansion without reliance on external funding. This model will support the platform's mission to revolutionize digital health tracking and improve early detection and management of endometriosis worldwide.

Planned Feature Developments

High Impact – High Effort

AI-Powered Prediction Models: Implement advanced AI-driven forecasting for menstruation and ovulation, offering more personalized cycle tracking and fertility insights.

Integration of FEMaLe Risk Profiles: Leverage big data research and AI models from the FEMaLe project to refine symptom analysis and support early endometriosis diagnosis.

Mid Impact – Mid Effort

Mindfulness Module Integration (MY-ENDO): Natively embed the successful MY-ENDO mindfulness program (WP8) for seamless user experience and enhanced retention, allowing symptom tracking alongside mental health insights.

Pregnancy Management Module: Expand pregnancy-related tracking features to support users from conception through pregnancy with personalized insights and tools.

Low Impact – Low Effort

App Theming: Introduce customizable UI themes and illustrations to enhance user personalization.

Core Enhancements for Growth

To retain existing users and accelerate market expansion, we will also focus on:

- *E-mail/Social Login:* Provide secure login options while maintaining encrypted and anonymized data storage.
- *Gamification:* Boost user engagement through avatars, achievements, point systems, and interactive elements.
- *Daily Tips & Personalized Insights:* Develop a content-driven advice system to provide relevant health information and support monetization through sponsorships.
- *Third-Party Data Integration:* Enable syncing with Google Calendar, Google Fit, Apple Health, and other fitness apps for a holistic health overview.
- *Formatted Data Export:* Allow users to export health records for personal use or private healthcare integration.
- *Educational Content Expansion:* Deepen existing health education materials, reinforcing Lucy's role in early diagnosis and self-care empowerment.

WP6 | DIAGNOSIS: machine learning automatic surgical phenotyping.

WP6 develops a machine-learning surgical phenotyping tool to enhance endometriosis diagnosis. While laparoscopy remains the gold standard, this AI-driven tool improves identification and classification, particularly for superficial endometriosis undetectable by MRI.

Innovation/technology: Machine learning-based algorithm for detection and scoring of endometriosis
See the outstanding result of *SURGAR's* business exploitation plan below.

WP7 | VISUAL: laparoscopic surgery using augmented reality.

Laparoscopy is a minimally invasive surgical technique offering reduced pain, fewer complications, and faster recovery compared to laparotomy. However, limitations such as 2D vision, reduced depth perception, and loss of tactile feedback pose challenges. Augmented reality (AR) can enhance laparoscopy by overlaying preoperative imaging (MRI, CT) onto live surgical views, improving precision. Partner *SURGAR* has developed software enabling AR integration in laparoscopy, allowing visualization of tumours and anatomical landmarks in real time. This technology, already applied to myoma and adenomyosis, is now being adapted for deep endometriosis, enhancing surgical safety, accuracy, and efficiency.

Innovation/technology: Machine learning-based algorithm suggesting endometriotic resection zone
SURGAR has secured €11 million in funding to accelerate the deployment of its AR solution for minimally invasive surgery and has obtained CE marking for its first software ([link to press release](#)). By merging a patient's digital twin (created from MRI or CT scans) with real-time laparoscopic views, *SURGAR's* AI-powered technology enhances surgical precision, making internal organ structures such as tumours, vessels, and ducts visible. This breakthrough aims to halve surgical complications and improve precision twentyfold, benefiting both patients — by reducing cancer recurrence and post-surgical complications — and healthcare providers through cost savings and increased efficiency.

The technology results from 12 years of research and collaboration between Clermont-Ferrand University Hospital and the EnCoV team at the Pascal Institute, with contributions from leading experts in AI, computer vision, and clinical practice. With multiple hospital collaborations underway in France and internationally, *SURGAR* is poised to revolutionize minimally invasive surgery. CEO Nicolas Bourdel emphasized that this milestone represents the culmination of long-term collaboration, introducing the first-ever AR solution for abdominal surgery.

WP8 | DIGITAL: self-management program

WP8 will develop and implement *MY-ENDO*, a digital self-management program empowering women with endometriosis to manage symptoms, improve quality of life, and reduce reliance on healthcare services. The MY-ENDO program aims to prevent chronic pain by addressing both physical and psychological symptoms.

Innovation/technology: MY-ENDO embedded into modified *Lucy App* (WP5)

As described on page 20, the next step is to natively embed the MY-ENDO program into the modified *Lucy App* for seamless user experience and enhanced retention, allowing symptom tracking alongside mental health insights.

6. The FEMaLe Legacy

FEMaLe Project has played a pivotal role in reshaping the landscape of endometriosis research and digital health innovation, demonstrating the value of integrating technology, patient engagement, and multidisciplinary collaboration to improve healthcare outcomes. Through its groundbreaking work in developing AI-driven diagnostic tools, digital self-management platforms, and personalized risk assessment models, FEMaLe has laid the foundation for two new major EU-funded projects that will further drive progress in women's health and inclusive research:

EUmetriosis: Transforming endometriosis care in Europe: an integrated approach to enhance understanding, diagnosis, tailored management and patient empowerment (€7M)

Endometriosis remains one of the most underfunded and least researched diseases despite its significant patient and socioeconomic burden, costing the EU €30 billion annually in sick leave alone. Decades of neglect, gaps in understanding its etiology and diagnosis, inadequate therapeutic options, and reliance on unproven self-management strategies have perpetuated challenges in care. To address these critical unmet needs, [*EUmetriosis*](#) employs a multi-pronged approach, integrating patient perspectives, clinical trials, advanced diagnostics, and digital health innovations.

By engaging patient organizations across Europe, *EUmetriosis* aims to explore perceptions of self-management amid the stigma and dismissal often experienced in clinical interactions. A randomized controlled trial will assess the effectiveness of dietary interventions and cognitive behavioral therapy on endometriosis-related pain and subfertility, while steroid metabolomics and microRNA profiling will enhance diagnostic capabilities and predict intervention outcomes.

Investigating the relationship between microbiota health, local epigenetic alterations, immune response, and endometriosis development will further clarify disease mechanisms. Leveraging eHealth technologies, AI, and machine learning, *EUmetriosis* will develop predictive models for lifestyle interventions, empowering patients to take control of their health while raising public awareness and reducing stigma.

Building on FEMaLe's achievements, *EUmetriosis* expands these efforts, aiming to transform endometriosis care through a holistic approach that enhances diagnosis, personalized management, and patient empowerment. By refining diagnostic pathways, integrating digital tracking and AI-assisted decision-making, and addressing long-standing gaps in care, *EUmetriosis* ensures that FEMaLe's research and technological advancements translate into real-world healthcare improvements, fostering earlier detection, more effective treatments, and greater patient-centered solutions.

READI: Research in Europe and Diversity Inclusion (€66M, €33M EU Contribution)

FEMaLe's advancements in endometriosis research, digital health, and patient-centered care have directly influenced [READI](#), a large-scale initiative fostering research excellence in Europe with a strong focus on diversity and inclusion. *READI* builds on FEMaLe's collaborative framework, promoting inclusive research practices to ensure underrepresented populations benefit from cutting-edge healthcare innovations.

The public-private partnership aims to address long-standing disparities in clinical studies (CS), which have struggled to recruit and retain participants from marginalized or disadvantaged communities, including sexual, gender, age, cultural, and socioeconomic groups. These knowledge gaps contribute to entrenched health disparities, limiting the effectiveness of research across different populations.

To tackle these challenges, *READI* will foster a more integrated and patient-centered CS ecosystem, actively connecting key stakeholders and providing essential tools, training, and approaches to improve recruitment and retention of underserved and underrepresented (US/UR) patients. A core component of the initiative is the development of an open, sustainable, and innovative digital platform, enhancing patient access to CS information, facilitating connections with research communities, and supporting long-term engagement. The effectiveness of *READI's* strategies will be tested in at least four clinical studies, ensuring real-world applicability.

The project has a three-fold objective:

- overcoming participation barriers in CS — such as lack of awareness, mistrust, poor communication, geographic limitations, and prejudice — thereby improving research across various diseases and demographic groups.
- enhancing preventive care and treatment effectiveness.
- benefiting society as a whole.

With a consortium of 73 organizations from 18 countries, spanning expertise in drug development, CS operations, US/UR population engagement, digital platform innovation, training, communication, ethics, and regulatory affairs, *READI* is poised to drive systemic change in clinical research, making it more inclusive, equitable, and impactful.

The direct evolution of FEMaLe into two ambitious projects (*EUmetriosis* and *READI*) highlights the sustainability and scalability of its outputs. By bridging the gap between technology, healthcare, and patient advocacy, FEMaLe has not only accelerated the development of endometriosis-specific interventions but has also contributed to a broader movement toward inclusive and patient-centered research in the EU. As these projects move forward, they will ensure that the knowledge, tools, and strategies developed under FEMaLe continue to drive meaningful change, enhancing both women's health and the inclusivity of European research initiatives.